

13,990-14,450 and 25,640-26,525 cm^{-1} respectively. Band I, which appears, as a single broad band with a tail extending far into the near infrared region, is considered to originate from the copper(II) ion in a distorted octahedral environment and is assigned to $d_{xz}, \overrightarrow{d_{x^2-y^2}}$ transition⁸. Band

II, however, appears as a shoulder on the lower energy side of the charge transfer band ($\text{O} \rightarrow \text{Cu}$) occurring in the ultraviolet region and provides conclusive evidence in support of the proposed binuclear structure. The band is assigned to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transition^{5,9}. The electronic spectra of the complexes recorded in methanol show only band I. This obviously arises from the conversion of the dimeric complexes into monomeric species as a result of solvent co-ordination. The diffuse transmittance spectra of QNO complexes reveal little difference from those taken in benzene solution, suggesting thereby that these complexes have identical structure both in benzene solution and solid state.

The N-O stretching vibrations occurring at 1250 and 1278 cm^{-1} in PNO and 3-MePNO and the P=O stretching vibration occurring at 1189 cm^{-1} in TPPO undergo a negative shift of 17-30 and 8-9 cm^{-1} respectively in their complexes indicating that these ligands are co-ordinated to copper(II) through their respective oxygen atoms. In QNO complexes, however, the $\nu(\text{N}-\text{O})$ is observed either at the same frequency (1232 cm^{-1}) as in the free ligand or is slightly shifted to higher wave numbers. This behaviour is typical of QNO-metal complexes and can be attributed to predominant $d_{\pi}-p_{\pi}$ back bonding from the metal to the ligand. However, $\delta(\text{N}-\text{O})$ shows large positive shifts confirming the co-ordination of QNO to copper(II) through its N-O oxygen. The asymmetric and symmetric carboxyl stretching frequencies appear as sharp and intense peaks in the regions 1626-1519 and 1432-1416 cm^{-1} respectively. The position, nature and separation ($\sim 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of these bands are characteristically similar to those of various 1:1 binuclear addition complexes of copper(II) acetate with oxygen donors⁵. All these investigations suggest that the complexes are binuclear carboxylate bridged species similar to that of copper(II) acetate monohydrate¹⁰.

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Syntheses of New Cobalt(III) Heterochelates Containing Three Different Bidentate Ligands in the Same Co-ordination Zone

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ALTHOUGH there has been considerable research interest in the syntheses and optical properties of cobalt(III) heterochelates of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{AA})_2(\text{BB})_2]^{n+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{BB})(\text{AA})_2]^{n+}$ (where $\text{AA} \neq \text{BB}$ = bidentate ligand) containing two different bidentate ligands in the co-ordination zone¹, very little is known about the cobalt(III) heterochelates of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{AA})(\text{BB})(\text{CC})]^{n+}$ (where $\text{AA} \neq \text{BB} \neq \text{CC}$ = bidentate ligand) containing three different bidentate ligands in the co-ordination zone. Only the complexes viz. $[\text{Co}(\text{en})(\text{tn})(\text{tetramethylenediamine})]^{3+}$, $[\text{Co}(\text{en})(\text{tn})(\text{neopentanediamine})]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{en})(\text{oxalate})(\text{glycine})]$ (where en = ethylenediamine and tn = trimethylenediamine) have been reported so far^{2,3}. The syntheses of such heterochelates containing three different bidentate ligands are of interest due to the following reasons:

(a) The stability of the M-L bonding in the heterochelates may be favoured in comparison to that in the homochelates, (b) the chromophore system is amenable to variation, (c) novel magnetic and spectral properties may develop due to the variation in the ligand field strength, (d) novel distortion may be noticed, (e) the charge of the complex cation can be varied by proper choice of ligands, (f) the heterochelates may serve as models for the naturally occurring metal-ternary or

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NOTES

TABLE I—THE ANALYTICAL, ELECTRICAL CONDUCTANCE AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COBALT(III) HETEROCHELATES

Complex	%Co	%N	%Halogen	Λ_M ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹	ν_{max} (e) cm ⁻¹
[Co(en)(pn)(bigH)]I ₃ ·H ₂ O ^a	Found : 8.2 Reqd. : 8.5	17.9 18.2	55.1 55.0	423	20410(158), 28570(156)
[Co(en)(pn)(acac)]I ₃ ·H ₂ O ^a	Found : 10.1 Reqd. : 10.5	9.7 9.9	45.1 45.0	259	20620(160), 20200(150)
[Co(en)(pn)(picam)]I ₃	Found : 8.3 Reqd. : 8.6	12.1 12.3	54.8 55.9	430	20200(150), 28985(180)
[Co(en)(pn)(tn)]I ₃	Found : 9.0 Reqd. : 9.1	12.8 13.0	57.7 58.8	430	20410(100)
[Co(en)(tn)(bigH)]I ₃	Found : 8.4 Reqd. : 8.7	18.5 18.7	55.2 56.4	425	20200(125), 28980(155)
[Co(en)(tn)(ophen)]I ₃	Found : 7.8 Reqd. : 7.8	11.0 11.1	50.1 50.5	401	20410(71)
[Co(en)(tn)(dipy)]I ₃ ·4H ₂ O ^a	Found : 7.2 Reqd. : 7.4	11.0 10.5	46.9 47.5	420	21830(130)
[Co(en)(tn)(acac)]I ₃	Found : 10.0 Reqd. : 10.5	9.8 9.9	45.1 45.0	260	21280(115)
[Co(pn)(tn)(ophen)]Cl ₃	Found : 11.8 Reqd. : 12.0	16.9 17.0	21.4 21.6	420	20100(120), 28640(170)
[Co(pn)(tn)(acan)]Cl ₃ ·2H ₂ O ^a	Found : 12.1 Reqd. : 12.0	14.0 14.3	14.1 14.5	235	20360(190)

(a) Satisfactory H₂O analysis was obtained by heating the complexes at 110°C for one hr. The loss of H₂O at 110°C indicates that H₂O exists as water of crystallization.

quarternary systems. In this preliminary communication we report the syntheses of several new cobalt(III) heterochelates containing three different ligands in the co-ordination zone, the ligands used being en, tn, propylenediamine (pn), orthophenanthroline (ophen), 2,2'-dipyridyl (dipy), acetoacetanilide (acan), acetylacetone (acac), biguanide (bigH), 2-guanidinobenzimidazole (gbm) and 2-picolylamine (picam).

General Method of Synthesis of the Complexes :

Trans-[CoCl₂(en)(tn)]Cl² or *trans*-[CoCl₂(en)(pn)]Cl⁴ or *trans*-[CoCl₂(tn)(pn)]Cl⁴ (0.01 mole) was dissolved in water (*ca* 4 cm³). The appropriate bidentate ligand (0.01 mole) was dissolved in water or 95% alcohol (10 cm³) and added to the above solution. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 7 by 2M NaOH solution and the mixture was heated on a water bath for 1-2 hr. This was cooled and the pH was adjusted to 6.5 by 2M HCl solution. On cooling in ice bath for 1 hr. crystalline chloride compounds were obtained in case of less soluble complexes. In case of the complexes where the chloride salts are not isolable at this stage due to high solubility in water, a solution of KI was added to the solution which resulted in the precipitation of the iodide complexes. The separated chloride and iodide compounds were filtered, washed with cold water followed by 95% EtOH and dried under vacuum. In case of biguanide aqueous solution of biguanide hydrochloride was used.

The analytical, electrical conductance and electronic spectral data of the complexes are presented in Table I.

The *trans*-[CoCl₂(en)(tn)]Cl, *trans*-[CoCl₂(en)(pn)]Cl and *trans*-[CoCl₂(pn)(tn)]Cl react with one molecule of bidentate neutral or monobasic ligand such as bigH, ophen, dipy, acan, acac, gbm, picam, en, pn, etc. and the heterochelates of the type [Co(AA)(BB)(CC)]²⁺ (where AA ≠ BB ≠ CC = bidentate ligand) are formed. These heterochelates are novel in the sense that these contain three different bidentate ligands in the same co-ordination zone. The complexes being cationic in nature is absorbed by cation exchange resin (amberlite IR 120, H⁺) and the equivalent weight of the complexes was determined by passing an aqueous solution of the complex through the resin and then titrating the eluate with standard sodium hydroxide solution. The observed equivalent weight values agree well with the calculated values. The molar conductance values of the complexes in aqueous solution are given in Table I and the values indicate bi-univalent or tri-univalent nature⁵ of the complex cations.

The electronic spectral data of the complexes are given in the Table I. The complexes exhibit one or two spectral bands at around 20000 and 28000 cm⁻¹ due to the spin-allowed transitions ¹T_{1g} ← ¹A_{1g} and ¹T_{2g} ← ¹A_{1g} respectively⁶. The high energy band cannot be located in some heterochelates as it is buried underneath the strong metal ligand charge transfer transitions. The complexes are diamagnetic as expected for six co-ordinate octahedral cobalt(III) complexes.

The isolation and characterization of other salts of the complex cations, chromatography, optical resolution and kinetics of dissociation of the

complexes are in progress and the details will be reported in due course.

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Equilibrium Studies between Ni(II)/Cu(II), 8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid and Histidine in Aqueous Solution

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8-HYDROXYQUINOLINE-5-SULPHONIC acid (HQSA) is well known chelating agent and its binary chelates have been studied quite extensively. However, so far the literature records very few solution equilibrium studies on the ternary complexes with HQSA as one of the ligands¹⁻⁶. During the present investigations, the pH-metric studies of the systems, Ni(II)/Cu(II) - HQSA - histidine (His) have been made.

Experimental

Metal salts (nitrates, AnalaR BDH) solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water and standardized with disodium salt of EDTA using murexide as indicator. HQSA (Kodak) was recrystallized from water and weighed out directly for

each investigation on account of its low solubility. Solution of histidine hydrochloride (BDH) was prepared by direct weighing and its strength was checked potentiometrically. Potentiometric titrations of the following solutions (total volume 50 ml) : (i) 10 ml (0.025 M) ligand, (ii) 10 ml (0.025 M) ligand + 10 ml (0.025 M), metal nitrate [M(II) - ligand, 1 : 1] where M(II) = Ni(II) or Cu(II) and (iii) 10 ml (0.025 M) each of primary and secondary ligands + 10 ml (0.025 M) metal nitrate [M(II) - primary ligand - secondary ligand, 1 : 1 : 1]; were carried out using a Systronics pH-meter. The ionic strength of the reaction mixtures was maintained approximately constant at 0.1 with potassium nitrate and the temperature at 30 ± 1° using a thermostat.

Results and Discussion

The dissociation constants of HQSA ($pK_1 = 4.06$, $pK_2 = 8.49$) and His (6.05, 9.17) were taken from literature^{4,7}. The pH-titration curves of solutions containing nickel nitrate and HQSA or His. HCl in equimolar proportions exhibit a sharp inflection at $m=2$ (m = moles of base added per mole of metal ion or ligand), followed by the buffer regions in the high pH-range. However, in case of solution containing copper nitrate, two inflections at $m=2$ and $m=3$ are observed. The inflection at $m=2$ in all cases indicate the formation of 1 : 1 complex. The inflection at $m=3$, or buffer region indicates the conversion of 1 : 1 complex into hydroxo derivative. In all these cases precipitation starts at $m \sim 2$.

The pH-titration curves of solutions containing nickel or copper nitrate in presence of equimolar concentrations of HQSA and His. HCl exhibit a sharp inflection at $m=4$, attributing the complete neutralization of both the protons of each of the ligands liberated as a result of chelation. All these curves run slightly above the corresponding 1 : 1 M(II)-HQSA titration curves in the beginning, which may be attributed to the presence of free tertiary and secondary amino groups in the His. HCl. This indicates that initially M(II)-HQSA (1 : 1) complexes are formed in the above systems. The lowering of these curves in comparison to the corresponding composite curves which is a measure of mixed ligand chelate formation, occurs after $m = 1.5$ in these systems, indicating the formation of the mixed ligand chelate species, which can only be 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes. The formation of the ternary complexes, thus, takes place in overlapping steps and through the formation of 1 : 1 M(II)-HQSA chelates. It also gets support by the analysis of the potentiometric data given below :

The formation of 1 : 1 : 1 mixed ligand chelate in the above systems may be represented as :

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